

EXPERIMENTAL/ANALYTICAL EXAMINATION OF RESIDUAL STRAINS IN COMPOSITE BONDED JOINTS

David H. Mollenhauer*, Greg A. Schoeppner*, and Endel V. Iarve**

* *Air Force Research Laboratory, WPAFB OH 45433-7750, USA*

** *University of Dayton Research Institute, Dayton, OH 45469, USA*

ABSTRACT: Residual strain predictions for composite adherends and an adhesively bonded composite joint are performed using thermomechanical linear elasticity. The analysis was performed using an in-house stress analysis program based on a polynomial spline displacement approximation method. The residual strain measurement was conducted by using the moiré interferometry technique. Diffraction gratings were replicated at room temperature onto the edge of polished laminated adherends and on the edge of a fully cured adhesively bonded specimen. The specimens were cut through their entire thickness in the middle of the diffraction grating area resulting in the relaxation of the residual curing strains at the edges of the cut. A full-field deformation pattern was obtained in the grating area by analyzing the recorded fringe patterns. A measure of the residual strains resulting from the adhesive bonding was obtained by subtracting the adherend results from the bonded results. The deformation field induced by the cut in the laminated adherends and the adhesive bondline can be estimated by the linear thermomechanical analysis. A good agreement between the analysis and the experiment was observed.

Key words: residual strains, bonded joints, moiré interferometry, three-dimensional analysis

INTRODUCTION

DoD initiatives to make composite aerospace structures more affordable, have focused on the design and manufacturing of highly unitized structures that eliminate fastener joints and costly shimming operations. As part of the effort focused on reducing part count and assembly time to lower manufacturing cost, there is an increased demand for utilization of structurally efficient adhesively bonded joints. The use of adhesively bonded joints in primary aircraft structures and in critical load paths has been limited to only a few production applications, such as in composite rotors for the rotorcraft industry. The primary bottlenecks for using adhesively bonded primary structure are firstly, the lack of an established nondestructive evaluation technique for quantifying the integrity of the adhesive bond and secondly, the inability to predict the long-term performance and damage tolerance of the adhesive joint under environmental/mechanical service loading. The long-range objective of the current program is to develop validated three-dimensional analysis tools that accurately predict the behavior and service life of composite bonded joints.

The majority of current design tools for composite bonded joints model composite adherends as homogenized orthotropic bodies and neglect the residual curing stresses within the adherends. It is unlikely that analysis procedures that neglect these residual curing stresses in the adherends and in the adhesive, particularly in free-edge regions, will be successful in accurately predicting failure initiation, damage propagation, and joint strengths [1]. The objective of the present study is to experimentally measure and analytically predict the free-edge residual strains in composite laminated and bonded specimens resulting from cutting the specimen edges. For thin symmetric laminates, residual curing stresses away from free-edges are nearly constant through the thickness of each ply and can be closely approximated using classical lamination theory. Near free-edges, both thermal residual and mechanical stresses are three-dimensional in nature and require full three-dimensional models to describe the stress/strain state. The ability to accurately predict the strain distribution in these complex three-dimensional regions of the specimens provides validation of residual stress and strain predictions for interior regions of the specimen having simpler stress and strain distributions.

The initial form of damage in composite laminates is believed to be micro-damage in the form of fiber/matrix debonds and matrix micro-cracks. The initial ply-level failure is typically transverse cracking and delamination resulting from the coalescence of micro-damage. The efficiency of designs of composite structures is highly dependent on the ability to accurately predict damage initiation and subsequent damage growth. Simple models that are incapable of capturing/representing the appropriate damage mechanisms, dictate the use of conservative design to mitigate uncertainties in the failure strength and damage tolerance. The development of design tools to accurately predict the performance of composite structures will require analysis methods that accurately describe ply-level, and possibly micro-level, stress and strain fields to allow for the prediction of damage formation. For instance Roy et al. [2,3] and others have reported that composite adherends fail on planes that are only a few fiber diameters from the adhesive/adherend interface. The use of models that represent the adherends as homogenized plates will not capture the governing failure initiation behavior and subsequent propagation of damage.

The B-Spline Analysis Method (BSAM) is a three-dimensional ply-level analysis program being developed by the Air Force Research Laboratory. The ply-level analysis in BSAM maintains continuity of strains and stresses throughout a homogenous ply while allowing strain discontinuity at ply interfaces in order to achieve interlaminar traction continuity, not achievable using conventional finite elements. Results from the BSAM program have been shown to be in excellent agreement with moiré interferometry ply-level results for open-hole composite laminate coupons [4,5]. The current effort is to analyze residual strain fields in a composite laminate and a composite bonded specimen using the BSAM analysis. The ply-level linear thermoelastic analyses are compared to moiré interferometry measurements of the strain field on the edge of the specimens and in the bondline region.

BSAM - SPLINE VARIATIONAL ANALYSIS METHOD

The BSAM computer code uses B-spline approximation basis functions to build a variable continuity approximation for laminated composite structures [6]. The displacement components are approximated by using piecewise polynomial three-dimensional functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum X_i(\mathbf{x})U_i \quad (1)$$

where U_i are displacement approximation coefficients, not necessarily associated with nodal displacements, and index i in Eq. (1) changes from 1 to the total number of approximation functions, which we will denote as a set Ω . Three-dimensional shape functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ are constructed from one-dimensional sets of B-spline basis functions of order n and defect k as standard tensor products. These one-dimensional approximations are built on subdivisions introduced in each coordinate direction. Polynomial splines of degree n over an interval $[a,b]$ with subdivision $a=x_0 < x_1 \dots < x_m = b$ are arbitrary piecewise polynomials of degree less than or equal to n at the intervals $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$, $i=0, m-1$. If the spline is constructed so that at every internal node x_i has $n-d_i$ continuous derivatives, then d_i is called the defect of the spline in the node x_i . The defect of the spline designates the maximum number of discontinuous derivatives over all nodes $k=\max\{d_i\}$. If the defect $k=1$, then $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \in C^{(n-1)}$; and in the case of $k=n$, one obtains the C^0 continuous traditional $p=n$ approximation. In general, the coefficients of the spline functions are not equal to the nodal values of the approximation function.

The utility of the spline approximation for the solution of boundary value problems is determined by the properties of the set of basis functions used in the analysis. B-spline basis functions, possessing the shortest possible support for a given power n and defect k , represent a computationally efficient analysis method (see Larve [6] for references). The minimum support length property provides maximum sparsity of the resulting system of equations. Another significant advantage of the B-spline basis is the ability to change the defect of the spline at the end nodes. This allows one to build a system of basis functions such that the displacements at the end nodes are the actual

coefficients of the spline functions, providing a convenient way of imposing boundary conditions by simply assigning spline function coefficients analogous to the traditional finite element approximation. It should be noted that the displacements in the internal nodes are not explicitly equal to the coefficients of the B-spline functions. A recurrent procedure based on polynomial representation (Iarve [6]) is used to build the set of B-spline basis functions of arbitrary order and defect. Each one-dimensional basis spline function is non-negative and possesses a local support of no more than $n-k+2$ nodal intervals. These one-dimensional basis functions as well as multidimensional ones, obtained as a tensor product of one-dimensional splines, represent a partition of unity with unit coefficients:

$$\sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \equiv 1, \quad \mathbf{x} \in V \quad (2)$$

Implementation of higher order continuity approximations requires C^0 boundaries in the case of complex geometries. A linear thermoelastic constitutive model was used to analyze the residual curing stresses and strains in the laminate and bonded specimens.

MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY EXPERIMENTS

Moiré interferometry is an optical interferometry technique capable of measuring in-plane surface displacements with high sensitivity [7]. A rigorous explanation of the physics and principles of moiré interferometry can be found in the literature [7,8]. The technique yields a displacement fringe pattern that is essentially a contour map of in-plane displacements in a given direction on the face of the specimen. Typically, fringe patterns are obtained in two orthogonal directions. In this research, x- and z-displacement fringe patterns were obtained during the experiment (see Fig. 1). Measures of the changes in displacement field on the edge of the specimens were obtained by subtracting the null or initial (*uncut*) displacement field from the loaded (*cut*) displacement field. Displacements are related to the x- and z-displacement fringe patterns by the following expressions.

$$U_x(x, z) = \frac{1}{f} N_x(x, z), \quad U_z(x, z) = \frac{1}{f} N_z(x, z) \quad (3)$$

where U_x and U_z are the displacements in the x- and z- directions, N_x and N_z are the fringe orders from the x- and z- displacement fringe patterns, and f is two times the frequency of the diffraction grating on the specimen (1200 lines/mm in this research). The change in strain on the specimen edge corresponding to the change in displacement is obtained by applying the linear elastic strain-displacement relationships.

Moiré interferometry has been used for measuring full-field residual strains for a variety of applications including thermal annealing strains in metal rails [9], in conjunction with a modified layer removal technique [10], and (most notable related to the current effort) evaluation of fiber-bundle level residual strains in a high temperature polymer matrix composite [11]. A comprehensive review of residual strain measurement techniques is given by Bowman [10].

FABRICATION OF THE COMPOSITE LAMINATES AND BONDED SPECIMENS

The material system used to fabricate the composite panel was IM7/5250-4 graphite/bismaleimide supplied in prepreg form. A 24-ply panel with a $[0/\pm 45/90]_{s3}$ stacking sequence was fabricated and cured in an autoclave. The panel was C-scanned after curing and found to be free of defects. Two 10.2-cm \times 10.2-cm adherend plates for bonding and two 5.0-cm \times 4.0-cm plates for evaluating adherend residual strains, were cut from the 24-ply panel. All specimens were stored in a desiccator to minimize moisture absorption that has the potential of altering the residual stress and strain state of the laminates.

The two 10.2-cm by 10.2-cm adherend plates were bonded together using 3 layers of AF-191-U adhesive film (thickness of film .20 mm). AF-191-U is an unsupported structural epoxy film adhesive manufactured by 3M. The adherends were bonded together such that the plate had an unsymmetrical

stacking sequence given by $[(0/\pm 45/90)_{S3}/Adh/(0/\mp 45/90)_{S3}]$. The adhesive of the bonded specimen was cured in the autoclave at 177°C. One of the 5.0-cm × 4.0-cm plates was placed in the autoclave during the adhesive cure cycle to determine the effect of the adhesive cure cycle on the adherend residual stresses and strains. After curing, the 10.2-cm × 10.2-cm adherend/adhesive plate assembly was C-scan and found to have isolated minor defects in the adhesive bondline. Two 50.8-mm × 25.4-mm specimens were cut from the 10.2-cm × 10.2-cm plate in regions that contained no defects. One of the 50.8-mm sides of each of the specimens was polished and a diffraction grating, necessary for the moiré technique, was applied to the edge of the specimen.

MOIRÉ TESTING AND BSAM MODELING

The elastic properties of the IM7/5250-4 graphite/bismaleimide were measured in an earlier test program. The ASTM D3039 and D3518 standard tests were used to measure all of the properties except ν_{23} . The ν_{23} Poisson's ratio was determined from a $[90_8]$ coupon under tension in which axial strain and transverse strain in the z-direction were measured using small strain gages (0.81 mm long). The transverse gage was mounted on the free-edge and two axial strain gages, one on the flat surface and one on the free-edge were mounted for comparison. Both axial strain gages gave nearly identical readings. The transverse ν_{23} was calculated by taking the negative of the transverse strain divided by the axial strain. The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) α_1 and α_2 were measured using strain gages in conjunction with a computer-controlled temperature chamber. The specimens were 5 cm by 5 cm and were tested over a temperature range of -118°C to 121°C. The measured room temperature material properties for the adherends used in the analyses are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 165.475 \text{ GPa}, & E_2 &= E_3 = 10.342 \text{ GPa} \\ G_{12} &= G_{13} = 5.7922 \text{ GPa}, & G_{23} &= 3.3095 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_{13} = 0.31, & \nu_{23} &= 0.56 \\ \alpha_1 &= 0.45 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}, & \alpha_2 &= \alpha_3 = 24.66 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

The thermomechanical properties of the AF-191-U adhesive material were measured over a temperature range from room temperature to 177°C. Temperature dependent stiffness properties of neat adhesive AF-191 were characterized by using uniaxial static tension tests at 20°C increments. The tests were conducted after 30-minute temperature stabilization periods. The Poisson's ratio and thermal expansion coefficients were also measured at the various temperatures and found to be nearly constant over the considered temperature range. The details of the testing and nonlinear adhesive properties are given in Bowman [10]. The room temperature AF-191-U material properties used in the analysis are:

$$E = 2.86 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu = 0.414, \quad \alpha = 81 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$$

The measured thickness of the cured 24-ply adherends was 3.287 mm and the measured in-situ thickness of the adhesive was 0.592 mm.

One edge of both of the 5.0-cm × 4.0-cm plates (one that was subjected to the adhesive cure cycle and one that was not) was polished and a diffraction grating applied. Each of the plates was placed in the moiré interferometer and a null displacement field was measured. The null displacement is a baseline measure of the apparent surface displacements resulting from surface irregularities and from the residual stresses caused by curing of the polymer diffraction grating. The null displacement field serves to zero out the initial displacement field from the *loaded* displacement field. The change in the displacement field due to loading is obtained by subtracting the null displacement field from the loaded displacement field. After taking null displacement field measurements of the two plates on the moiré interferometer, a slit was cut through the plates as shown in Fig 1. The displacement field on the surface of the specimen after the cut represents the *loaded* displacement field. The cut was made using a 0.38-mm thick diamond saw blade. The cut was made dry to avoid water or cooling solution absorption by the laminate or by the diffraction grating polymer. The saw was operated at a very low speed to avoid localized heating of the specimen and to minimize damage to the diffraction grating at the edges of the cut. The introduction of the slit changes the localized stress and strain fields, and the relaxation of the localized residual curing stresses is manifested in changes to the local displacements.

A slit rather than a complete cut was made so as not to change the overall dimensions of the specimen so that it could be easily placed back into the moiré interferometer holding fixture used to measure the null displacement field. A measurement of the *loaded* displacement field was made immediately after the specimen was cut.

A comparison of the cut induced strain fields of the two plates showed that there was no measurable difference in the strains between the specimens. It was concluded that the adhesive cure cycle had negligible effects on the residual stresses and strains in these laminate specimens. Therefore, it is also assumed that the adhesive cure cycle has negligible effects on the residual stresses in the laminate adherends of the bonded specimen. As noted previously, all specimens were stored in a desiccator to minimize moisture absorption. Measurement of the *loaded* displacement field for specimens stored in the desiccator for extended times, showed no notable changes from the displacement fields measured immediately after cutting. Therefore, it is believed that minimal relaxation of the residual stresses occurred in the specimens and that they behave in a linear elastic manner for the room temperature dry conditions.

Although it is still some matter of contention, the temperature at which laminates are stress-free is generally accepted to be at or slightly below the maximum curing or post-curing temperature for the majority of composites. Residual stress development during the curing process has been studied by numerous researchers, including early work by Hahn and Pagano [12]. The objective of much of this work is to reduce the residual stresses in an effort to enhance the mechanical performance of composites, and in particular, the onset of failure. Although the effect of chemical shrinkage during the curing process manifests itself in microcracks during processing, amongst other phenomenon, it is generally not accounted for in stress or failure predictions. The use of an effective ΔT , defined as the difference between the use temperature and the stress-free temperature, can be used to account for the cumulative cure shrinkage and residual stress effects. Additionally, for relatively thin laminates, it is assumed that the residual curing stresses are based on the ply-level mismatch in CTE and that the difference between ambient and stress-free temperature is uniform throughout laminates. For the current study, an effective ΔT of -155°C was used.

Figure 1: Laminate plate edge cut

Figure 2: Bonded specimen edge cut

The difference between the effective CTE of the composite adherends and the CTE of the adhesive results in residual stresses in the adhesive bondline as well as added residual stresses in the composite adherends. An effective ΔT of -155°C was used to calculate the residual stress and strain fields in the adherends and the adhesive resulting from the adhesive curing process. A procedure similar to that used for the laminate plates to measure the residual free-edge strains, was used for the bonded specimen using the configuration shown in Figure 2. The measured bonded specimen strain field includes the combined strains due to the laminate/adherend curing process and the adhesive curing process. Knowing the moiré strain field results of the laminated plate specimens (which have identical residual strain fields as the bonded specimen adherends) and the strain field results of the bonded joint specimen allows one the opportunity to isolate of the effects of the adhesive cure on the residual strain fields. This is accomplished by numerically/graphically subtracting the residual strain fields of the composite adherends from the residual strain field of the bonded joint. The resulting strain field is that due to the adhesive curing process only. Although the results from this procedure are not shown in this article, they will be shown in future articles.

To model the laminate and bonded specimens, a three-dimensional BSAM model was developed in which each ply of the specimens was modeled as a separate homogeneous orthotropic three-dimensional body. Quadratic spline interpolation functions for all three directions of the displacement approximations were used, resulting in a quadratic distribution of the through-the-thickness displacement (z -direction, see Fig 2) in each ply of the adherends. However, the interpolation was refined in the thickness direction for the adherend plies adjacent to the adhesive and for the adhesive layer. This was necessary due to the steep strain gradient in this region resulting from the adhesive/adherend CTE mismatch. Additionally, refinement near the free-edges of the x - y plane, where the experimental strain measurements were recorded, was required. Given the effective ΔT , we need only to use the room temperature linear elastic properties of the laminates since the cut was made and the stresses relax at room temperature.

ANALYTICAL/EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

Based on the stacking sequence of the laminate, it is expected that the experimental and analytical results will have some distinguishing characteristics. Firstly, the laminate has three repeating sublaminates with a stacking sequence of $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$, as illustrated in Figure 3. Since the laminate has no out-of-plane loading in the z -direction, it is expected that the strain field through the thickness of the laminate would manifest this same repeating behavior, assuming there is no material variability through the thickness based on processing orientation. Secondly, the strain fields on opposite sides of

the cut are not expected to mirror each other, based on differences in the free-edge conditions and stacking sequence effects on the two sides as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 5 shows a contour plot of the experimentally measured surface displacements U_x and U_z in the region of the cut for the laminated plate specimens. It can be seen that the in-plane displacement U_x appears similar on both sides of the cut. The U_x displacements on the left side of the cut clearly indicate some variability in the properties of the laminate as a function of the z -direction. The measured displacements in the bottom sublaminate resulting from the cut do not extend as far from the cut free-edge as the displacements in the top two sublaminae. These variabilities may be due to variations in the local fiber volume content and/or due to the tool-part interaction during the panel cure [13]. This variability will be addressed in future work. The U_z displacement clearly shows significant differences in the displacement field on the two free-edges of the cut. These differences in the displacement fields are also manifested as differences in the strain fields on the two free-edges of the cut.

Figure 6 shows contour plots of the in-plane ε_x strains determined from the measured moiré displacement field and of the predicted ε_x strains from the BSAM analysis. The BSAM results show that the cut affects the strain field farther from the free-edge than the experimental results. However, the strains in these regions far from the free-edge are small and not significant. The moiré results indicate a higher concentration of strains in the center of the sublaminae on the right free-edge of the cut (evidenced by the larger blue region) than the concentration of strains on the left free-edge of the cut. The BSAM results show the same trend. Figure 7 is a comparison plot of the ε_x strains along lines close to the free-edge on the left and right sides of the cut. The strains are plotted at a distance of 0.1 mm from the left and right free-edges denoted at $x_L = -0.1mm$ and $x_R = 0.1mm$, respectively. It can be seen that the linear elastic BSAM analysis is able to accurately predict the sublaminate variations and closely

Figure 3: Repeating sublaminate

Figure 4: Stacking sequence dependent edge conditions

In-plane displacement, U_x

Through-the-thickness displacement, U_z

Figure 5: Measured displacement field for laminated plate (adherend) specimen after cut

Moiré results

BSAM results

Figure 6: Comparison of the axial strain ε_x for the laminate plate

Figure 7: Comparison of axial strain ε_x near the free-edge

predict the magnitudes of the in-plane strains. Similar comparison plots for ε_z and γ_{xz} at various distances from the free-edges show that the linear elastic analysis consistently predicts the qualitative z -direction variability of the strains. The analysis accurately predicts the magnitude of the strains for most cases; however for some cases, the predictions underestimate the magnitudes of the ε_z strain by as much as 50 percent. The differences in the predicted versus measured results may result from limitations of the linear elastic analysis as applied to the material system used in this study. The IM7/5250-4 material system requires an elevated temperature post-cure and the effective ΔT used in the predictions is suspect. These differences will be addressed in a future program that will utilize a different thermoset material system and determine the repeatability of the relaxation measurements.

Figure 8 shows the in-plane U_x displacement field for the bonded specimen. The figure shows the total thickness of the top adherend, the adhesive, and part of the bottom adherend. The in-plane displacements in the free-edge region of the top adherend are very similar to that of Figure 5 as expected. The differences in the colors between Figures 5 and 8 are due to the arbitrary selection of

Figure 8: In-plane displacement U_x for the bonded specimen

the zero displacement point (strains are only dependent on displacement gradients not displacement magnitudes). It can be seen that in the region of the adhesive layer (the shaded area) and regions within the adherends show close contour lines indicating large strain gradients. Again, the variation of the axial and transverse strains through the thickness of the adherends in the experimental contour

plot support the argument that a ply level analysis is required. In particular, a homogenized analytical representation of the composite adherends would not capture the detailed residual strain release shown in the figures. The BSAM analysis shows favorable agreement of strains for both the left and right side free-edge region of the cut.

DISCUSSION

The residual curing strains for adherend and bonded specimens are investigated with a novel experimental technique and a 3-dimensional stress analysis. The results illustrate the importance of using a ply-level analysis to describe the residual strain and stress fields. Good agreement between the predicted and experimentally determined through-the-thickness strain variation was obtained. Future work will address the limitations of the linear thermoelastic analysis and observed discrepancies between the experimental results and predictions.

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